

Comparitive Study of Pre-Engineered Building and Truss Arrangement Building for Varying Spans

Submitted in fulfillment of the requirements
for the Degree of
Master of Engineering in Civil Engineering
(With Structural Engineering Subjects)

By
Roshni Ramakrishnan

Under the Guidance of
Dr. P. A. Dode

Department of Civil Engineering
Datta Meghe College of Engineering

Sector 3, Airoli, Navi Mumbai-400708

University of Mumbai

April 2022

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the dissertation titled “**Comparitive Study of Pre-Engineered Building and Truss Arrangement Building for Varying Spans**” is a bonafide work of **Roshni Ramakrishnan** is submitted to the University of Mumbai in fulfillment of the requirement for the award of degree of **Master of Engineering in Civil Engineering(with Structural Engineering Subjects)**.

Dr. P. A. Dode

Professor (Guide)

Dr. P. A. Dode

Professor and Head(Civil)

Dr. S. D. Sawarkar

Principal

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I hereby declare that the work presented in this Dissertation “**Comparitive Study of Pre-Engineered Building and Truss Arrangement Building for Varying Spans**” has been carried out by me under the supervision of Professor Dr. P. A. Dode. This is my own contribution and has not been submitted by me to Mumbai University for the award of any diploma/degree.

Roshni Ramakrishnan

Date:

Place: Airoli, Navi Mumbai

DATTA MEGHE COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING

SECTOR 3,AIROLI,NAVI MUMBAI-400708

DISSERTATION APPROVAL SHEET

This Dissertation entitled “**Comparitive Study of Pre-Engineered Building and Truss Arrangement Building for Varying Spans**” by **Roshni Ramakrishnan** is approved for the degree of Master of Engineering in Civil Engineering (with Structural Engineering Subjects).

Internal Examiner

External Examiner

Date:

Place: Airoli, Navi Mumbai

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ABSTRACT

Steel has been gaining massive popularity over RCC due to the very advantages it offers like malleability, re-usability, fire resistance and so on. Pre-Engineered building is a type of building system which employs built-up sections for the structural members which are engineered and manufactured at factories and assembled at site. This results in a good quality control and saves a lot of time. A rigorous study on past research works related to Pre-Engineered buildings showed a lack of research on the effectiveness of Pre-Engineered building system for smaller and larger span buildings and most comparative works being between Pre-Engineered building system and conventional steel building system. Hence the present study focuses on comparison between PEB and Truss arrangement building system so as to arrive at an economic building system configuration for a building of a given span and size. For the research work, three plan dimensions 15x30m, 40x80m and 90x180m for an industrial pitched roof building are considered and each checked for a PEB and truss arrangement building configuration and a detailed comparative study is undertaken. The software Staad.Pro connected edition is used for the 3D modelling of the building system and the Indian standards IS 800-2007, IS 875:Part 1:1987, IS 875:Part 2:1987, IS 875:Part 3:2015, IS 1893:2002 are used for the application of loads. The dissertation provides a detailed comparative study of the analysis results, deformations and material take off and subsequently the effectiveness of Pre-Engineered building system for a building of a given span and size. The subsequent results are tabulated for easy interpretation of values for achieving the required aims and objectives.

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ABBREVIATIONS

PEB	Pre-Engineered Building
CSB	Conventional Steel Building
RCC	Reinforced Cement Concrete
C _{pe}	External Wind Pressure
C _{pi}	Internal Wind Pressure
F _x	Force in x direction
F _y	Force in y direction
F _z	Force in z direction
M _x	Moment about x axis
M _y	Moment about y axis
M _z	Moment about z axis
L/C	Load Combination

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 General

The advent from RCC to Steel in Construction industry started taking place from the 1880s, with the very first use in bridges. The advantages provided by steel like longer spans, good malleability, re-usability, better quality control, fire resistance, lesser weight and hence greener than RCC and so over years it has gained popularity and is being massively used in construction industry. Steel finds its use in high rise buildings with composite construction used for most of the multi-risers, Pre-Engineered Buildings for industrial sheds, large span structures like hangars, bridges etc. The Pre-Engineered buildings are those which are engineered and manufactured at factories and assembled at site. Built-up, hot rolled sections, cold formed sections are used in such buildings and the section differs along length as the section size is dependent on the bending moment profile. Overall the cost of construction gets simplified due to simplification in fabrication & erection and also saving in time due to quicker delivery of the components which are usually from a single source. Past research has shown that for large span, a reduction of 20%-30% in steel quantity and also 30%-50% saving in time of project due to faster delivery and quicker site erection. Due to the simplification in erection and maintenance, Pre-Engineered Buildings are becoming the preferred choice over the past few years over conventional steel building.

1.2 History

Pre-Engineered systems were first used for farming structures and then gained popularity as storage sheds because of the huge fire resistance ability of steel. The Austin company in Ohio was one of the first to come up with standard Pre-Engineered commercial buildings. Pre-Engineered buildings were developing throughout 20th century and became largely popular around the time of second world war. The advent of computer aided design made it possible to come up with customized designs as per requirements.

1.3 Typical structural configuration of PEB

The various parts of PEB are as follows:

FIG 1.1:VARIOUS PARTS OF A PRE- ENGINEERED BUILDING

Primary Structural Elements:

Main/Gable End Frame-It provides vertical support and stability along lateral direction. The frame is made up of built up I sections.

Secondary Structural Elements:

1) Purlins/Girts

The purlins and girts support roofing sheeting and wall sheeting respectively. They span between the main frames and are usually made of cold formed steel sections. They constitute 10% to 25% of total steel quantity.

2) Eaves strut

It is used to support eaves gutter.

3) Bracing system

It provides longitudinal stability. Side wall and roof bracing are provided at the same location. Angles and rods can be used for bracing.

4) Roof and Wall cladding system

It is used to transfer wind loads from secondary members to main frame members.

Chapter 2

Review of Literature

2.1 General

The research study as briefed in successive section is done on the topics of advancements in steel building sector,important parameters considered in the design of steel buildings,the effect of various parameters on the performance of the building system, geometric optimizations,need for Pre-Engineered Buildings, advancements in the sector of Pre-Engineered Buildings and previous comparative studies between Pre-Engineered Buildings and other building system configuration types. Through the research study,it is intended to understand the important parameters in steel design,effective lateral load resisting system to be considered for a building system ,optimization procedure and further research studies needed on the topic of concern of Pre-Engineered Buildings.

2.2 Review of published work

Beedle et al. (1973) explained the need for ways other than re-sizing the members for optimization. Some of the techniques for optimization suggested are:

- 1) Use ways to capitalize strength and ductility
- 2) Exploit the potentials of load factor and limit states of design
- 3) Consider stiffness contribution of walls, partitions and floors acting with structural frames
- 4) Utilization of additional strength that can be exploited in bi-axial columns
- 5) Interior beam to column connection need not have stiffeners

6) Going for optimal geometric configuration

Andrew W et al. (1993) explains the preliminary design procedure adopted by architects to design steel buildings. It helps us understand the necessary parameters required for design of steel members. Resist is a program used by architects to do preliminary sizing of members. Some of the assumptions made for the preliminary sizing of members are:

- 1) Building height is less than 30m
- 2) Only one type of structural system is permitted along each direction
- 3) Structural Diaphragm is assumed at each floor level transferring lateral loads to vertical elements
- 4) Lateral load resisting systems used are structural walls, Moment resisting frames and Braced frames
- 5) Lateral loads- Basic wind speed is taken as average over a selection of spots
- 6) Ductility factors assumed are as per Ultimate Limit State

RC frame = $\mu = 6$

Steel frame = $\mu = 3$

Shear wall = $\mu = 5$

Ajizaz Ahmad et al. (2013) carried out a comparative study between PEB and Conventional steel frame building. The following conclusions were deduced:

- 1) PEB gives lighter sections and hence effect of seismic Forces is reduced
- 2) It was deduced that for building of length 80m with Columns provided at 8m, 8.88m, 10m, 11.425m and 13.3m, 8.8m and 11.425m gave economy
- 3) It was observed that 27% reduction in steel took place
- 4) In case of long span structures, PEB gave more economy
- 5) Weight of PEB depends on bay spacing with increase beyond a certain limit increases weight of steel

Balwant Kumar et al. (2013) Through review of literature on BOQ, it was seen that BOQ was used for post tender activities like costing, bonusing, ordering & programming. The benefits of PEB in optimization of BOQ are

- 1) Increased speed of construction & quicker returns on investments
- 2) Ensured quality control
- 3) Relatively easy construction, maintenance and refurbishing
- 4) Single source responsibility

Kavya Rao et al. (2014) carried out a comparative study between Pre-Engineered building and conventional steel building. The following were the observations:

- 1) PEB reduces steel used by 36% than that required by conventional steel building
- 2) The analysis forces are lesser in PEB as compared to Conventional Steel Building
- 3) Since the reactions in PEB are lesser due to lighter sections used, foundations are comparatively lighter
- 4) Delivery time is as follows
PEB- 6 to 8 weeks
CSB- 20 weeks
- 5) 30% cost reduction was observed in PEB as compared to CSB.

Swapnil N.Dhande et al. (2015) compared the various bracing systems for seismic lateral forces acting on industrial steel buildings to arrive at economical bracing system. The model considered is a portal frame of span 16m and 7 bays spaced at 4m c/c with ceiling height and rise of 8m and 3.2m respectively. The lateral force resisting configurations considered are cross diagonal (CD), single diagonal (SD), Inverted vertical V bracing (INVB) and vertical V bracing (VVB)

- 1) Time period for the models decreased as follows:

Model	Time period
Unbraced	0.834
INVB	0.585
VVB	0.581
SDB	0.553
CDB	0.433

- 2) There was a better overall performance with the provision of bracing with the responses reducing considerably with CDB.
- 3) The analysis results of shear, moment and axial forces reduced in order of Unbraced, SDB, VVB, INVB and CDB.

Pradeep S. et al. (2015) took up the study of various types of roof trusses like Warren, N, Pratt and Howe truss systems. It was seen that the Warren truss is most economical among all.

Thi Thi Hein Lwin et al. (2015) undertook study to find the effect of mass irregularity on the performance of high-riser. It was observed that

- 1) Storey drift is 1.65 times more for irregular than regular

- 2) Storey shear is 1.27 times more than that of a regular structure for an irregular structure
- 3) Storey moment is 1.3 times more than regular structure for an irregular structure
- 4) Storey displacement is 1.72 times more for an irregular structure than that for regular
- 5) Mode shapes are such that the time period is 1.09 s for irregular and 0.862s for regular.

Donald W. White et al. (2015) The various elastic analysis and design methods for stability analysis are explained throughout the study which is summarized as follows:

1) Direct Analysis Method

It can be applied to all types of frames. It includes two modifications to include second order effects. It uses a reduced Elastic modulus of 0.8 factor and the initial out of plumbness is taken as $L/500$

2) Effective length method

The method is related to elastic buckling stress equation. It is used when $\Delta_2/\Delta_1 < 1.5$ where Δ_2 is displacement due to second order effects and Δ_1 is displacement due to first order effects.

Isha Rohilla et al.(2015) carried out study on effects of presence of vertical irregularity in the form of floating columns. The following are the observations:

- 1) Floating columns should be avoided in high rise buildings in zone 5 because of its poor performance
- 2) Storey displacements and drifts increase due to floating columns
- 3) Storey shears are decreasing due to reduction in mass
- 4) Increasing size of beams and columns at level of floating columns and consecutive floors above help to reduce drifts

Rasool Owais et al.(2016) did a comparative study of the following lateral load resisting systems 1) Bare frame 2) Shear wall at corners 4) Bracings at corners. The following observations were made:

- 1) The nodal displacements both translational and rotational motions were least for shear walls
- 2) The analysis forces of moments, shear forces were found to be least in bracing lateral load resisting system
- 3) The relative displacements for bracing system are lesser
- 4) Reduced base shear and moments could be produced on using bracing system

Aditya P Mehendale et al. (2016) carried out study on maintenance procedures of Pre-Engineered Buildings. The procedure adopted is as follows:

- 1) Waste and small items like screws, pop rivets, drill bits, ferrous objects are removed by sweeping with nylon brush
- 2) Large items like metal cut outs are removed by hand
- 3) Sand and dust removed by water
- 4) Mild detergents are used to remove saline deposits

Vishal Kumar et al. (2016) carried out a comparative study of various types of Pre-Engineered buildings and the following conclusions were deduced:

- 1) For PEB, equivalent Von Misses is tensile
- 2) Arched frame helps in 8.84% saving in steel.
- 3) Monoslope frames consume 1.3 times more steel than regular

Khuzaim J. Sheikh et al. (2017) carried study on a 60 storey tall structure with the following types of load resisting systems like rigid frames, core wall, shear wall along width of each block, shear wall along length of each block, shear wall at corners, tube structure and outrigger system. The most efficient one was found to be the shear wall at corners followed by tube structural system.

Cyrille F. Dunant et al. (2018) undertook a study of steel framed buildings to check on the extend of optimal usage of steel sections and the areas where optimization can be carried out. The following are the observations:

- 1) Improving structural design helps to lower carbon foot print. It depends on capabilities of design firm, the norms and codes, time allotted, the budget and preferences of client. Using plastic design helps to save the structural steel work.
- 2) 79 steel framed buildings were analyzed and reasons for high Utilization Ratio are
 - 1) Rationalization- It involves using the same sections over large spans. Usually the section used is the one following highest requirements:
 - 2) Usage of built-up sections instead of standard hot rolled sections.
 - 3) Members at ends can use lighter sections.
 - 4) Secondary beams can be optimized to maximum extend.

Anil V. Bandre et al. (2019) carried out a study to compare design using hot rolled steel section and built up sections. It has been concluded that the shear force, bending moment and displacements are comparatively lower in PEB than in using hot rolled steel section.

Umesh L.Mali et al. (2020) carried out a comparative study between various lateral load resisting systems for varying heights. The following conclusions were deduced:

- 1) For buildings in the range of 20m to 35m height- Shear walls are efficient
- 2) For buildings in the range of 20m- X Bracings are efficient
- 3) X bracing is most efficient in high seismic zones
- 4) Concrete outrigger system is more efficient than steel
- 5) U,L Shapes are more critical

S.No.	Year	Name of Researcher	Research Paper	Scope of Research
1	1973	Beedle,Lynn S, Lu, Le- Wu, Ozer, Erkan	Recent Developments in Steel Building Design - AISC	The research discusses the improvements that can be done in steel building design. The improvements are categorized into strength & ductility, limit states, Interaction equations and optimized structural system.
2	1993	Andrew W Charleson	Vertical lateral load resisting elements for low to medium rise buildings- Information for architects - Bulletin of the New Zealand Society for Earthquake Engineering 26(3) :356-368	It provides details about the information that is used for initial design of steel buildings. RESIST, a computer program designed for this purpose is used for the study.

3	2013	Ajizaz Ahmad Zende Prof A.V. Kulkarni Aslam Hutagi	Comparative Study of analysis and design of Pre-Engineered Buildings and Conventional frames - IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering	Study on steel reduction and economy between PEB and Conventional Steel Building for long span structures.
4	2013	Balwant Kumar N. N. Harry Y. K. Bind R. K. Pandey	Opimization of Bill of Quantities for Pre construction of Pre Engineered Buidings - International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology	It shows the variations in BOQ due to the use of Pre-Engineered building over conventional steel building.
5	2015	Swapnil N.Dhande Y R.Suryavanshi Pravin S Ptil	Industrial Building Design on seismic issues- International Journal of Innovative Research in	Comparitive study of various lateral load resisting systems on industrial buildings subjected to seismic forces.

6	2015	Pradeep S Monika N.R	Science, Engineering and Technology Design and Comparison of various types of long span roof trusses - International Journal of Science and Engineering Research	Comparative study of various roof configurations and arriving at the most economical configuration.
7	2015	Thi Thi Hein Lwin Kyaw Lin Htat	Study on effect of high rise steel building with different masses-Journal of science, Engineering and Technology Research	Study on effect of vertical irregularities on structural response of steel multi-risers.
8	2015	Donald W. White Andrea E.Surovet Bulent N.Alendar Ching Jen Kim Yoon Duk Kim	Stability Analysis and Design of Steel Building Frames using 2005 AISC Specifications	A study on the analysis methodology for consideration of P Delta effects on the steel building elements.

		Garret H.K.Kuchenbecker		
9	2015	Isha Rohilla S. M. Gupta Babita Saini	Seismic response of multi-storey irregular building with floating column- International Journal of Research n Engineering and Technology	The research was undertaken to study the effect of floating columns on structural performance and ways to reduce drifts and forces due to presence of floating columns.
10	2016	Rasool Owais Tantray Manzoor Ahmad	Comparative Analysis between different commonly used lateral load resisting systems in Reinforced Concrete Buildings-Global Journal of Researches in Engineering:Civil and Structural Engineering	The aim of the study was to arrive at the most efficient lateral load resisting system.

11	2016	Aditya P Mehendale Dr. A.K.Gupta Prof. D.B. Desai	Assessment & maintenance of Pre-Engineered buildings- National Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development	A description of the maintenance of procedure applied to the steel structures is given.
12	2016	Vishal Kumar Bhaskarbhair Patel	Parametric Study of various Pre-Engineered buildings- International Journal of Advance Research in Computer Science and Management	The steel building was checked for various configurations like PEB, Arched frames, monoslope and the best configuration is arrived at.
13	2017	Khuzaim J. Sheikh Kosha S.Pachchigar Bijal Chardhari Unnati D Bhagat	A review on study of lateral load resisting systems in tall structures- International Journal of Advance Engineering and Research	The study was undertaken to find the most efficient lateral load resisting arrangement in tall buildings.

16	2018	Cyrille F.Dunant Michael P.Drewniok Slathis Eleftheriadis Jonathan N. Cullen Julian N.Allwood	Development Regularity and optimisation practice in steel structure frames in real design cases	The research paper focuses on the extend of optimization done across the steel building and the need for optimisation.
17	2019	Mittal Parmar Varsha Yadav Samruddha Rajee	A parametric study on Pre- Engineered building - International Journal of Technical Innovation in Modern Engineering & Science	Study of various building configuration and its effects on saving of steel and economy.
18	2019	Anil V. Bandre Girish Joshi	Study for comparison on design of steel frame using rolled,fabricated & PEB sections- International Journal of trends in Scientific	The study intends to see the variation in results on using PEB built up sections as compared to hot rolled sections.

19	2020	Umesh L.Mali S. N. Patil	Research & Development Review on lateral load resisting systems for different geometric shapes of high rise buildings- ISSN:2321-9939 IJEDR (International Journal of Design Engineering & Research)	The study takes up various lateral load resisting systems and their efficiency for various heights of buildings is checked.
20	2014	Kavya Rao K.N. Vishwanath	Design Optimisation of an Industrial Structure from Steel Frame to Pre-Engineered Building	The research involves the comparative study between PEB and Conventional Steel Building involving the study of reduction in analysis forces, steel take off and the delivery time.

After the rigorous study of previous research papers related to the topic under consideration, it was observed that most of the research studies have been related to the effectiveness of Pre-Engineered Buildings over the Conventional Steel Buildings. There have not been many research works related to the effectiveness of Pre-Engineered building system over the Truss arrangement building system with respect to the span and size of the building. Hence the present work touches upon the previously mentioned topics over which the extend of research work has been found to be less.

Chapter 3

Problem Statement

3.1 General

From the detailed literature study as summarized in the preceding chapter, it has been observed that there is a general lack of study on the effectiveness of Pre-engineered buildings over Truss arrangement buildings and the economy in using Pre-engineered system for varying span and size of buildings. Hence the present research touches upon the aforementioned areas to arrive at effective conclusions.

3.2 Problem Statement

After the exhaustive study work on Pre- Engineered steel buildings, the topic of present dissertation is taken as “**Comparitive Study of Pre-Engineered Building and Truss Arrangement Building for varying spans**”. It involves a comparative study of industrial pitched roof steel building designed as Pre- Engineered building with Built-up I sections and Conventional steel building with truss arrangement system for varying spans. For the analysis purpose, three plan dimensions of 15x30m, 40x80m and 90x180m are considered. The loads are calculated using Indian standard codal provisions.

In the following proposed study:

- 1) An industrial pitched roof steel building is designed for plan dimensions of 15x30, 40x80 and 90x180 as Pre- Engineered building and truss arrangement building. In total 6 models are prepared for the analysis purpose.

- 2) For the design guidelines, the codes used are IS 800-2007, IS 875:Part 1:1987 (Second Revision), IS 875:Part 2:1987 (Second Revision), IS 875:Part 3:2015 (Third Revision), IS 1893 (Part 1):2002
- 3) The structural models are designed for Dead loads, Live loads, Wind loads and Earthquake loads.
- 4) The models are analyzed and designed in software STAAD.Pro Connect Edition.
- 5) The results from the analysis are studied in detail.

3.3 Aim and Objectives:

The aim of the study is the comparative study of pre-engineered building and truss arrangement building for varying spans.

The objectives of the project are as follows:

- 1) To study the effectiveness of Pre-Engineered Building system for smaller span buildings.
- 2) To study the effectiveness of Pre-Engineered Building system for larger span buildings.
- 3) To do a detailed comparative study between the two structural building systems for varying spans in terms of variation in analysis results.
- 4) To find the economical advantage in adopting Pre-Engineered Building system over Conventional Building system for a building of given span and dimensions.

3.4 Scope of work:

Through the achievement of the and objectives as explained in the previous section, the scope of project undertaken is as follows:

- 1) Detailed study of results between Pre-Engineered and Truss arrangement buildings with respect to variation in span of the building.
- 2) The effectiveness in using PEB for smaller span buildings.
- 3) Arrive on a conclusion on the most efficient and economical structural configuration for an industrial building with pitched roof for a given span and dimensions.

Chapter 4

Modelling and Analysis

4.1 Skeletal modelling

The spans of 15x30m,40x80m and 90x180m are considered. A uniform height of 7m and bay spacing of 6m are considered for all models. Using these dimensions the primary members of columns,rafters,bracing and truss elements shall be modeled in STAAD.Pro Connect Edition software.The structures are modeled as 3-D structures. Hinged support is provided for the columns in PEB models as hinge support helps to get an optimal structural design. The grade of steel used is E350.

4.2 Loads:

Major loads considered are:

- 1) Dead load - 1.682kn/m on rafters and 1.05 kn/m on columns
 - 2) Live load - 4.5kn/m for PEB1&CSB1, 1.682kn/m for PEB2&CSB2 and PEB3&CSB3 acting on on rafters
 - 3) Wind load - Design wind pressure of 1.382 kn/m²
 - 4) Seismic load - As per Seismic Coefficient Method using Indian codal provisions
- A)Dead Loads: It consists of Self Weight,connections and other accessories.IS 875 (Part 1) will be used as reference for final dead loads.Roof load consists of sheeting (0.5 mm thick galvalume), purlins,sag rods & fly bracings.Column load consists of cladding (0.5mm thick galvalume),girts,sagrods & flybraces.

B)Live Load: Live loads are produced due to occupancy of the people and other structures which are movable. IS 875 (Part 2) will be used for calculation of live loads. Here the roof load is taken as per the provisions in code. The eaves gutter is not assumed in the model and hence all associated loads to be neglected.

C)Wind Load:

IS 875(Part 3) deals with wind loads to be considered when designing building structures and components thereof.

D)Static Seismic Analysis

Seismic load: The seismic forces shall be calculated in accordance with IS 1893(part 1). This code deals with assessment of seismic load on various structures and earthquake resistant design of buildings.

4.3 Review of modelling and analysis with STAAD.Pro Connect Edition:

STAAD.Pro is a comprehensive and integrated finite element analysis and design offering that includes a state-of-the-art user interface, visualization capabilities and international design codes. It is capable of analyzing any structure exposed to static, dynamic, wind, earthquake, thermal and moving loads. STAAD.Pro provides structural analysis and design for any type of project, including towers, buildings, culverts, plants, bridges, stadiums and marine structure.

4.4 Procedure to perform analysis:

- 1) The industrial building will be modeled as a PEB with elements of varying section sizes so as to get optimum economy and as a truss configuration system in STAAD.Pro Connect Edition.
- 2) All section sizes are to pass as per Indian Standard Design Criteria with Utilization less than 1.
- 3) The deflection limits shall be considered from IS 800:2007 table 6 and the deflections are kept within limits.
- 4) The analysis results are studied and the intended aims and objectives are found.

4.5 Numerical Problem

The industrial building having pitched roof is designed as a Pre-Engineered Building with built-up I sections and as a roof truss arrangement for the following data.

Plan dimensions- 15x30, 40x80 and 90x180

Height of building- 7m

Max bay spacing- 6m

Roof slope - 1 in 5 15X30,40X80, 1 in 10 90x180

Location- Chennai

4 sided cladding

Cladding and roofing sheet- 0.5mm thick Galvalume Sheet

Purlin and girt section used is 200ZS60x2(Cold form steel section)

Steel design and Load combinations- IS 800-2007 and IS I893:2002

4.6 Models considered in the analysis are:

Model 1a)PEB for plan dimensions 15x30m (Refer STAAD.Pro File PEB1)

Model 1b)Truss bldg for plan dimensions 15x30m (Refer STAAD.Pro File CSB1)

Model 2a)PEB for plan dimensions 40x80m (Refer STAAD.Pro File PEB2)

Model 2b)Truss bldg for plan dimensions 90x180m (Refer STAAD.Pro File CSB2)

Model 3a)PEB for plan dimensions 90x180m (Refer STAAD.Pro File PEB3)

Model 3b)Truss bldg for plan dimensions 90x180m (Refer STAAD.Pro File CSB3)

4.7 Summary

The study involves comparison of Pre-Engineered building system with truss arrangement building system for various spans.The Pre-Engineered models are optimized for most economical configuration by variation of the geometric parameters(depth,width,flange and web thickness)and the truss arrangement models' section profiles are found using the analysis software. The models are compared for arriving at the aims and objectives of the study undertaken.

Model 1a)PEB for plan dimensions 15x30m - PEB1

Model 2a)PEB for plan dimensions 40x80m - PEB2

Model 2b) Truss bldg for plan dimensions 40x80m - CSB2

Model 3a)PEB for plan dimensions 90x180m - PEB3

Model 3b) Truss bldg for plan dimensions 90x180m - CSB3

Chapter 5

Detailed Methodology

The loads considered to be acting on the building are dead, live, wind and seismic loads. The calculations for the loads are as follows:

5.1 Dead Loads

1) Self weight and a multiplication factor of 1.15 is taken to account for the weight of connections.

2) Weight of roofing sheet = 0.5mm thick galvalume sheet

Assume weight of galvalume sheet as 5kg/m²

Assume weight of sag rods, flange braces etc as 5kg/m²

Assume weight of collateral load as 10kg/m²

Total = 20kg/m²

u.d.l on main rafter = 0.2×6

$$= 1.2 \text{ kn/m}$$

u.d.l on gable end rafter = $0.2 \times 6/2$

$$= 1.2 \text{ kn/m}$$

Load due to purlins =

No. of purlins = $(7.64/1.5) + 1$

$$= 6.093 \sim 6 \text{ (Assume purlins spaced at 1.5m c/c)}$$

Self weight of lipped Zed section 270x75x20x2.55 = 8.77kg/m (Refer

IS811(1987))

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Main rafter} &= (6 \times 8.77 \times 7 \times 10) / (1000 \times 7.64) \\ &= 0.482 \text{ kn/m}\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Gable end rafter} = 0.24 \text{ kn/m}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total load on main rafter} &= 1.2 + 0.482 \\ &= 1.682 \text{ kn/m}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total load on gable end rafter} &= 0.6 + 0.24 \\ &= 0.84 \text{ kn/m}\end{aligned}$$

3) Weight of side wall sheet = 0.5mm thick galvalume sheet

$$\text{Side wall sheet} = 5 \text{ kg/m}^2$$

$$\text{Sag rods, flange braces etc} = 5 \text{ kg/m}^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total} &= 10 \text{ kg/m}^2 \\ &= 0.1 \text{ kn/m}^2\end{aligned}$$

Girts are located at 1.5m c/c

Girt load = no. Of girts x spacing x weight/column height

$$\text{Height of column} = 7 \text{ m}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{No. of purlins} &= 7 / 1.5 + 1 \\ &= 5.66 \sim 6\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Purlin load on main column} &= 6 \times 6 \times 8.77 \times 10 / 7 \times 1000 \\ &= 0.45 \text{ kn/m}\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Purlin load on gable end column} = 0.225 \text{ kn/m}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total load on main column} &= 0.45 + 0.6 \\ &= 1.05 \text{ kn/m}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total load on gable end column} &= 0.225 + 0.3 \\ &= 0.525 \text{ kn/m}\end{aligned}$$

5.2 Live Loads

Live load is taken from IS 875 (Part 2) - Table 2. As per the table for flat, sloping or curved roof up to and including 10 degrees with access not provided, a uniformly distributed load of 0.75 kn/m² is taken and for slopes greater than 10 degrees, 0.75 kn/m² less 0.02 kn/m² for every degree increase in slope over 10 degrees subject to a minimum of 0.4 kn/m². The live loads applied are as follows:

For PEB1 and CSB1 models - 4.5 kn/m for mid bay and 2.25 kn/m for gable end bay

For PEB2 and CSB2 models - 1.682 kn/m for mid bay and 0.84 kn/m for gable end bay

For PEB3 and CSB3 models- 1.682 kn/m for mid bay and 0.84 kn/m for gable end bay

5.3 Wind load calculations (IS 875 (part 3))

Location= Chennai

Wind basic speed(V_b)= 50m/s

Probability factor(k_1)= 1

Terran roughness and height factor(k_2)= 1

Topography factor(k_3)= 1

Importance factor for cyclonic region(k_4)= 1.15 (Industrial Building)

$V_z = V_b \times k_1 \times k_2 \times k_3 \times k_4$

$$= 50 \times 1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 1.15$$

$$= 57.5 \text{ m/s}$$

Wind pressure(p_z)= $0.6 \times V_z^2$

$$= 0.6 \times 57.5^2$$

$$= 1.988 \text{ kn/m}^2$$

$P_d = k_d \times k_a \times k_c \times p_z$

k_d (wind directionality factor)= 1 (The area of location is cyclone affected)

K_a =area averaging factor

Least tributary area= 7×6

$$= 42 \text{ m}^2$$

Tributary area(m ²)	k_a
25	0.9
42	x
100	0.8

K_a =0.87 by interpolation

K_c =0.8

$P_d = 1.983 \times 1 \times 0.87 \times 0.8$

$$= 1.38 \text{ kn/m}^2$$

Assume opening as 5-20%

Internal pressure coefficient= +/-0.5

For h/w= 0.466

l/w= 30/15= 2

The wind load calculations for rafters and columns are tabulated in the succeeding tables.

TABLE 5 : WIND LOAD CALCULATIONS FOR COLUMNS AND RAFTERS

Wind angle Θ (degrees)	Cpe for surfaces			
		B	C	D
0	+0.7	-0.25	-0.6	-0.6
90	-0.5	-0.5	+0.7	-0.1

WIND LOAD CALCULATIONS FOR RAFTER

Wind Angle	Cpe	Cpi +	Cpi -	Cpe + Cpi +	Cpe + Cpi -	Pd(kn/m ²) (Cpe+ Cpi+)	Pd(kn/m ²) (Cpe+ Cpi-)	Spacing (m)	Wd(kn/m ²) (Cpe+ Cpi+)	Wd(kn/m ²) (Cpe +Cpi-)
0deg EF	-0.8	+0.5	-0.5	-1.3	-0.3	-1.794	-0.41	6	-10.76	-2.46
0deg GH	-0.4	+0.5	-0.5	-0.9	0.1	-1.24	+0.138	6	-7.44	0.82
90deg EG	-0.8	+0.5	-0.5	-1.3	-0.3	-1.79	-0.41	6	-10.74	-2.46
90deg FH	-0.4	+0.5	-0.5	-0.9	0.1	-1.24	+0.138	6	-7.44	0.82

WIND LOAD CALCULATIONS FOR COLUMNS

Wind Angle & Surface	Cpe	Cpi +	Cpi -	Cpe+ Cpi+	Cpe+ Cpi-	Pd(kn/m ²) (Cpe + Cpi+)	Pd(kn/m ²) (Cpe+ Cpi-)	Spacing (m)	Wd(kn/m ²) (Cpe+ Cpi+)	Wd(kn/m ²) (Cpe+ Cpi-)
0deg A	+0.7	+0.5	-0.5	0.2	1.2	0.27	1.65	6	1.62	9.9
0deg B	-0.25	+0.5	-0.5	-0.75	0.25	-1.03	0.34	6	-6.18	2.04
0deg C	-0.6	+0.5	-0.5	-1.1	-0.1	-1.51	-0.138	6	-9.06	0.828
0deg D	-0.6	+0.5	-0.5	-1.1	-0.1	-1.51	-0.138	6	-9.06	-0.828
90deg A	-0.5	+0.5	-0.5	-1	0	-1.38	0	6	-8.28	0
90deg B	-0.5	+0.5	-0.5	-1	0	-1.38	0	6	-8.28	0
90deg C	+0.7	+0.5	-0.5	0.2	1.2	0.276	1.65	6	1.65	9.9
90deg D	-0.1	+0.5	-0.5	-0.6	0.4	-0.82	0.55	6	-4.92	3.3

5.3 Seismic parameters considered (IS1893-2002/2016)

Response Reduction factor= 4

Importance factor= 1

Rock and soil site factor=2

Type of structure= 2

Damping ratio(DM)= 0.05

Region= Chennai

5.4 Servicing checks

Refer table 6 from IS 800 for deflection checks.

For rafters, the permissible deflection is taken as span/180.

For columns, the permissible deflection is taken as span/150.

The models are applied the loads are calculated in the previous sections using STAAD.Pro Connect Edition with user interface features for the application of dead, live, wind and seismic loads.

The pre-engineered models are designed after assigning the design parameters of as follows:

L_z, K_z (Effective length along z direction for columns and rafters respectively) = Full length of columns and length of rafters from tie to tie

L_x, K_x (Effective length along x direction for columns and rafters respectively) = 1.5m
(The cold formed purlins are spaced at 1.5m c/c)

L_y, K_y (Effective length along y direction for columns and rafters respectively) = 1.5m
(The cold formed purlins are spaced at 1.5m c/c)

F_y (Yield Strength of Steel) = 350000 kn/m²

F_u (Ultimate Strength of Steel) = 490000 kn/m²

The design is done as per the provisions of hot rolled steel section. The members are further optimized to give the utility ratio close to 1.

The conventional steel building models are given similar parameters. The assign profile feature is used to design the steel models. The succeeding figures give the schedules for the steel member profiles for the final models.

Fig 5.1 - Steel Column Layout plan and shedule at base level for PEB1
Fig 5.2 - Steel Column Layout plan and shedule at rafter level for PEB1
Fig 5.3 - Rafter and bracing layout plan shedule for PEB1
Fig 5.4 - Gable end elevation for PEB1
Fig 5.5 - Intermediate bay elevation for PEB1
Fig 5.6 - Column plan layout and shedule at base level for CSB1
Fig 5.7 - Shedule of bracings and tie members for CSB1
Fig 5.8 - Section at gable end for CSB1
Fig 5.9 - Section at mid span for CSB1
Fig 5.10 - Column layout plan and shedule at base level for PEB2
Fig 5.11 - Column layout plan and shedule at
Fig 5.12 - Shedule of rafters and bracings for PEB2
Fig 5.13 - Section at gable end for PEB2
Fig 5.14 - Section at mid span for PEB2
Fig 5.15 - Column plan layout and shedule at base level for CSB2
Fig 5.16 - Shedule of bracings and tie members for CSB2
Fig 5.17- Section at gable end for CSB2
Fig 5.18 - Section at mid span for CSB2
Fig 5.19 - Column plan layout and shedule at base level for PEB3
Fig 5.20 - Column plan layout and shedule at rafter level for PEB3
Fig 5.21 - Shedule of rafters and bracings for PEB3
Fig 5.22 - Section at gable end of PEB3
Fig 5.23 - Column plan layout and shedule at base level for CSB3
Fig 5.24 - Shedule of bracings and tie members of CSB3
Fig 5.25 - Section at gable end for CSB3
Fig 5.26 - Section at mid span for CSB3

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

STEEL COLUMN LAYOUT PLAN AT BASE LEVEL

SCHEDULE OF COLUMNS

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
C-01	300	6	220	16
C-02	206	12.5	204.3	12.5

Fig 5.1 - Steel Column layout plan and shedule at base level for PEB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SCHEDULE OF COLUMNS

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
C-03	350 - 450	7	350	18
C-02	206	12.5	204.3	12.5

Fig 5.2 - Steel column layout plan and shedule at rafter level for PEB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SCHEDULE OF RAFTERS

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
R1	450 - 350	7	350	18
R2	300	6	220	16

SCHEDULE OF BRACINGS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
CB1	2 ISA 100 x 100 x 10 (STAR)
T1	2 ISA 90 x 90 x 8 (STAR)

Fig 5.3 - Rafter and Bracing layout plan and shedule for PEB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 01

Fig 5.4 - Gable End Elevation for PEB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 02

Fig 5.5 - Intermediate bay elevation for PEB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SCHEDULE OF COLUMNS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
C-01	2 ISA 60 x 40 x 5 (— —)
C-02	2 ISA 50 x 50 x 7 (— —)
C-03	2 ISA 35x 30 x 4 (— —)

Fig 5.6 - Column plan layout and shedule at base level for CSB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SCHEDULE OF BRACINGS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
CB1	2 ISA 60 x 60 x 8 (— —)
T1	2 ISA 50 x 35 x 5 (— —)

Fig 5.7 - Shedule of bracings and tie members for CSB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 01

SCHEDULE OF ROOF TRUSS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
a	2 ISA 40 x 35 x 5 (_ _)
b	2 ISA 20 x 20 x 5 (_ _)

Fig 5.8 - Section at gable end for CSB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 02

SCHEDULE OF ROOF TRUSS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
CB1	2 ISA 60 x 40 x 6 (_ _)
T1	2 ISA 20 x 20 x 5 (_ _)

Fig 5.9- Section at mid span for CSB1

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

STEEL COLUMN LAYOUT PLAN AT BASE LEVEL

SCHEDULE OF COLUMN

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
C-01	750	12	400	30
C-02	393	22.6	399	36.5
C-04	950 - 750	12	400	25

Fig 5.10 - Column layout plan and shedule at base level

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

PLAN LAYOUT AT RAFTER LEVEL

SCHEDULE OF RAFTER

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
R1	400 - 300	6	300	14
R2	300	6	300	14
R3	650 - 360	6	360	16

SCHEDULE OF BRACINGS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
CB1	2 ISA 120 x 120 x 10 (SA)
T1	2 ISA 90 x 90 x 6 (SA)

Fig 5.11 - Column layout plan and shedule at rafter level for PEB2
45

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

RAFTER & BRACING LAYOUT PLAN

SCHEDULE OF RAFTER

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
R1	950 - 750	12	400	30
R2	800 - 750	10	450	30
R3	750 - 1400	10	450	30

SCHEDULE OF BRACINGS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
CB1	2 ISA 150 x 150 x 16
T1	2 ISA 80 x 80 x 6

Fig 5.12 - Schedule of rafters and bracings for PEB2

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 01

Fig 5.13 - Section at gable end for PEB2

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 02

Fig 5.14 - Section at midspan for PEB2

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

PLAN LAYOUT AT BASE LEVEL

SCHEDULE OF COLUMN

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
C-01	2 ISA 60 x 60 x 8 (_ _)
C-02	2 ISA 80 x 60 x 8 (_ _)

Fig 5.15 - Column plan layout and shedule at base level

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

PLAN LAYOUT AT RAFTER LEVEL

SCHEDULE OF BRACING

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
CB1	2 ISA 80 x 60 x 10 (_ _)
T1	2 ISA 80 x 60 x 8 (_ _)

Fig 5.16 - Shedule of bracings and tie members for CSB2

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 01

SCHEDULE OF ROOF TRUSS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
a	2 ISA 60 x 60 x 8 (_ _)
b	2 ISA 40 x 35 x 5 (_ _)
c	2 ISA 50 x 35 x 5 (_ _)

Fig 5.17 - Section at gable end for CSB2

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 02

SCHEDULE OF ROOF TRUSS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
a	2 ISA 80 x 80 x 10 ()
b	2 ISA 35 x 30 x 4 ()
c	2 ISA 60 x 60 x 8 ()

Fig 5.18 - Section at mid span for CSB2

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

STEEL COLUMN LAYOUT PLAN AT BASE LEVEL

SCHEDULE OF COLUMN

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
C-01	750	12	400	30
C-02	393	22.6	399	36.5
C-04	950-750	12	400	25

Fig 5.19 - Column plan layout and shedule at base level for PEB3

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

STEEL COLUMN LAYOUT PLAN AT RAFTER LEVEL

SCHEDULE OF COLUMN

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
C-03	850 - 950	12	400	30
C-02	393	22.6	399	36.5
C-04	950 - 750	12	400	25

Fig 5.20 - Column plan layout and shedule at rafter level for PEB3

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

RAFTER & BRACING LAYOUT PLAN

SCHEDULE OF RAFTER

NAME	D (mm)	TW (mm)	BF (mm)	TF (mm)
R1	950 - 750	12	400	30
R2	800 - 750	10	450	30
R3	750 - 1400	10	450	30

SCHEDULE OF BRACINGS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
CB1	2 ISA 150 x 150 x 16
T1	2 ISA 80 x 80 x 6

Fig 5.21 - Schedule of rafters and bracings of PEB3

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

PLAN LAYOUT AT RAFTER LEVEL

SCHEDULE OF BRACING

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
CB1	2 ISA 150 x 150 x 20 (L L)
T1	2 ISA 150 x 150 x 16(L L)

Fig 5.24 - Shedule of bracings and tie members of CSB3

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 01

SCHEDULE OF ROOF TRUSS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
a	2 ISA 40 x 35 x 5 (_ _)
b	2 ISA 20 x 20 x 5 (_ _)

Fig 5.25 - Section at gable end for CSB3

Note:
All dimensions are in mm

SECTION ON GRID - 02

SCHEDULE OF ROOF TRUSS

NAME	STANDARD INDIAN STEEL SECTION
a	2 ISA 200 x 200 x 25 (—)
b	2 ISA 90 x 90 x 6 (—)
c	2 ISA 150 x 150 x 16 (—)

Fig 5.26 - Section at mid span for CSB3

Chapter 6

Results and Discussions

6.1 Introduction

STAAD.Pro Connect Edition is used to do a comparative study of Industrial buildings of spans 15x30m, 40x80m and 90x180m designed as Pre -Engineered Building and Conventional Truss Building Structures. The structures are subjected to wind and seismic loads apart from the dead and live loads as per Indian Standard Codal provisions. The structures are checked for economy on the basis of support reactions, member deflections, member forces and steel take off. The results are presented and discussed in the chapter. In this chapter the variation in the analysis results and subsequent influence on the material takeoff is discussed.

6.2 Results and discussions

The height of the buildings is kept as 7m and spacing of bays as 6m c/c throughout. The location is taken as Chennai ,India for analysis purpose. The dead loads considered are due to purlins & girts and 0.5mm thick galvalume sheet and subsequent dynamic forces of wind and earthquake are calculated as per Indian Standard provisions and applied on structures. The parametric study results are as follows:

6.2.1 Comparison of Base Reactions

The tables 6.1 and 6.2 give the reaction summary for models PEB1 and CSB1 which is maximum F_x , F_y and F_z values which represent the reaction forces along x, y and z with F_x , F_z representing horizontal reaction forces and F_y giving the vertical reaction force.

TABLE 6.1 : REACTION SUMMARY FOR PEB1

	Node	L/C	Horizontal	Vertical	Horizontal	Moment		
			F_x (kN)	F_y (kN)	F_z (kN)	M_x (kNm)	M_y (kNm)	M_z (kNm)
Max F_x	11	69:GENERATE	84.135	94.293	-0.034	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min F_x	11	65:GENERATE	-62.443	26.506	0.004	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max F_y	11	56:GENERATE	66.819	191.192	-0.060	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min F_y	11	5:W.L.(0+CPI)	-37.556	-84.642	0.026	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max F_z	1	71:GENERATE	-3.212	68.475	61.693	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min F_z	1	67:GENERATE	3.452	-7.356	-61.749	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max M_x	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.011	-15.406	-15.006	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min M_x	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.011	-15.406	-15.006	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max M_y	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.011	-15.406	-15.006	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min M_y	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.011	-15.406	-15.006	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max M_z	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.011	-15.406	-15.006	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min M_z	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.011	-15.406	-15.006	0.000	0.000	0.000

TABLE 6.2 : REACTION SUMMARY FOR CSB1

	Node	L/C	Horizontal	Vertical	Horizontal	Moment		
			F_x (kN)	F_y (kN)	F_z (kN)	M_x (kNm)	M_y (kNm)	M_z (kNm)
Max F_x	145	14:GENERATE	176.117	-257.063	-38.052	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min F_x	150	16:GENERATE	-164.803	-239.464	20.664	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max F_y	1	14:GENERATE	1.701	473.211	69.041	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min F_y	145	14:GENERATE	176.117	-257.063	-38.052	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max F_z	1	16:GENERATE	-8.694	438.034	84.849	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min F_z	110	16:GENERATE	-8.694	423.647	-70.148	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max M_x	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-7.216	-2.177	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min M_x	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-7.216	-2.177	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max M_y	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-7.216	-2.177	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min M_y	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-7.216	-2.177	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max M_z	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-7.216	-2.177	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min M_z	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-7.216	-2.177	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum horizontal forces of Fx and Fz for PEB1 are 84.135Kn and 61.749Kn respectively and for CSB1 are 176.117Kn and 84.849Kn respectively. The Fx and Fz are lesser by 52.22% and 27.22% respectively in PEB1 as compared to CSB1. The maximum vertical reactions for PEB1 and CSB1 are 191.92Kn and 473.211kn respectively and thus the vertical reaction in PEB1 is lesser by 59.44% as compared to CSB1.

The tables 6.3 and 6.4 give the reaction summary for models PEB2 and CSB2 which is maximum Fx, Fy and Fz values which represent the reaction forces along x, y and z with Fx, Fz representing horizontal reaction forces and Fy giving the vertical reaction force.

TABLE 6.3 : REACTION SUMMARY FOR PEB2

	Node	L/C	Horizontal	Vertical	Horizontal	Moment		
			FX (kN)	FY (kN)	FZ (kN)	MX (kNm)	MY (kNm)	MZ (kNm)
Max FX	14	27:GENERATE	86.037	110.922	-3.824	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FX	30	23:GENERATE	-55.956	29.702	-0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FY	59	16:GENERATE	-20.893	485.307	0.035	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FY	59	7:W.L.(90+CPI)	17.454	-212.795	-0.028	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FZ	1	29:GENERATE	-3.365	135.317	124.519	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FZ	1	25:GENERATE	3.859	-88.072	-124.519	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MX	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-0.054	-28.072	-23.973	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MX	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-0.054	-28.072	-23.973	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MY	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-0.054	-28.072	-23.973	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MY	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-0.054	-28.072	-23.973	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MZ	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-0.054	-28.072	-23.973	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MZ	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-0.054	-28.072	-23.973	0.000	0.000	0.000

TABLE 6.4 : REACTION SUMMARY FOR CSB2

	Node	L/C	Horizontal	Vertical	Horizontal	Moment		
			FX (kN)	FY (kN)	FZ (kN)	MX (kNm)	MY (kNm)	MZ (kNm)
Max FX	280	26:GENERATE	468.755	-420.577	-47.565	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FX	282	28:GENERATE	-449.596	-419.560	8.663	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FY	1	26:GENERATE	4.253	1.14E+3	528.023	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FY	34	28:GENERATE	43.470	-772.707	330.026	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FZ	2	28:GENERATE	21.735	1.13E+3	540.345	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FZ	261	26:GENERATE	4.253	1.14E+3	-528.906	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MX	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-30.520	-15.825	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MX	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-30.520	-15.825	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MY	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-30.520	-15.825	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MY	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-30.520	-15.825	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MZ	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-30.520	-15.825	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MZ	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	0.000	-30.520	-15.825	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum horizontal forces of Fx and Fz for PEB2 are 86.037Kn and 124.519Kn respectively and for CSB2 are 468.755Kn and 540.345Kn respectively. The Fx and Fz are lesser by 81.64% and 76.95% respectively in PEB2 as compared to CSB2. The maximum vertical reactions for PEB2 and CSB2 are 485.307Kn and 1140kn respectively and thus the vertical reaction in PEB2 is lesser by 57.42% as compared to CSB2.

The tables 6.5 and 6.6 give the reaction summary for models PEB3 and CSB3 (90x180m) which is maximum Fx, Fy and Fz values which represent the reaction forces along x, y and z with Fx, Fz representing horizontal reaction forces and Fy giving the vertical reaction force.

TABLE 6.5 : REACTION SUMMARY FOR PEB3

	Node	L/C	Horizontal	Vertical	Horizontal	Moment		
			FX (kN)	FY (kN)	FZ (kN)	MX (kNm)	MY (kNm)	MZ (kNm)
Max FX	7	26:GENERATE	488.311	722.577	-89.047	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FX	73	28:GENERATE	-348.311	587.052	70.494	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FY	447	28:GENERATE	-75.902	1.11E+3	-0.215	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FY	447	7:W.L.(90+CPI)	46.793	-453.244	0.121	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FZ	1	32:GENERATE	15.689	371.702	240.911	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FZ	1	34:GENERATE	-7.920	-245.372	-240.904	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MX	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-7.222	-195.164	-160.605	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MX	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-7.222	-195.164	-160.605	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MY	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-7.222	-195.164	-160.605	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MY	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-7.222	-195.164	-160.605	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MZ	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-7.222	-195.164	-160.605	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MZ	1	1:E.Q.(Z+)	-7.222	-195.164	-160.605	0.000	0.000	0.000

TABLE 6.6 : REACTION SUMMARY FOR CSB3

	Node	L/C	Horizontal	Vertical	Horizontal	Moment		
			FX (kN)	FY (kN)	FZ (kN)	MX (kNm)	MY (kNm)	MZ (kNm)
Max FX	2143	27:1D.L.+1W.L	484.614	-254.950	-17.220	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FX	2132	25:1D.L.+1W.L	-571.868	-206.107	31.710	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FY	1	24:1D.L.+1L.L	139.739	389.984	136.263	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FY	1	25:1D.L.+1W.L	-321.512	-920.125	-335.256	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max FZ	2064	25:1D.L.+1W.L	-329.830	-898.647	240.053	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min FZ	1	25:1D.L.+1W.L	-321.512	-920.125	-335.256	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MX	1	24:1D.L.+1L.L	139.739	389.984	136.263	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MX	1	24:1D.L.+1L.L	139.739	389.984	136.263	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MY	1	24:1D.L.+1L.L	139.739	389.984	136.263	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MY	1	24:1D.L.+1L.L	139.739	389.984	136.263	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max MZ	1	24:1D.L.+1L.L	139.739	389.984	136.263	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min MZ	1	24:1D.L.+1L.L	139.739	389.984	136.263	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum horizontal forces of Fx and Fz for PEB3 are 488.311Kn and 240.911Kn respectively and for CSB3 are 571.868Kn and 335.256Kn respectively. The Fx and Fz are lesser by 18.52% and 28.14% in PEB as compared to CSB3. The maximum vertical reactions for PEB3 and CSB3 are 1110Kn and 920.125Kn respectively and thus the vertical reaction in PEB3 is greater by 20.63% as compared to CSB3.

The support reaction forces are greatly reduced until span of 40m. For 90x180m building, steel truss building showed lesser reaction forces as compared to Pre-Engineered building. The lesser reaction forces result in smaller plate thickness and weld sizes and hence better economy.

6.2.2 Comparison of displacements

The tables 6.7 and 6.8 give the nodal displacement summary for the rafters of PEB1 and CSB1 models. The maximum and minimum displacements in x,y and z directions for the nodes are extracted with the tables giving the critical load combination corresponding to each node.

TABLE 6.7: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR PEB1(RAFTER)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	13	42:1D.L.+1WL	41.599	0.166	-0.009	41.599	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min X	19	44:1D.L.+1WL	-12.315	0.095	0.683	12.334	0.000	0.000	0.001
Max Y	15	42:1D.L.+1WL	38.320	17.149	-0.304	41.984	-0.000	0.000	0.001
Min Y	15	38:1D.L.+1LL	-0.572	-27.048	0.222	27.055	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Z	5	50:0.8LL.+0.8\	-6.404	-1.030	2.146	6.832	-0.000	0.000	-0.000
Min Z	30	38:1D.L.+1LL	-0.250	-3.842	-1.579	3.977	-0.001	-0.000	-0.000
Max rX	5	38:1D.L.+1LL	-0.250	-3.842	1.491	3.944	0.001	0.000	-0.000
Min rX	30	38:1D.L.+1LL	-0.250	-3.842	-1.579	3.977	-0.001	-0.000	-0.000
Max rY	4	50:0.8LL.+0.8\	-6.205	0.009	0.984	6.280	-0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rY	3	50:0.8LL.+0.8\	-6.592	-0.016	0.925	6.657	-0.000	-0.000	0.000
Max rZ	48	38:1D.L.+1LL	1.456	-16.871	0.010	16.735	0.000	0.000	0.005
Min rZ	47	38:1D.L.+1LL	-2.589	-16.831	0.010	17.026	0.000	-0.000	-0.005
Max Rst	15	42:1D.L.+1WL	38.320	17.149	-0.304	41.984	-0.000	0.000	0.001

TABLE 6.8: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR CSB1(RAFTER)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	58	38:1D.L.+1LL	4.673	-1.052	-0.104	4.893	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min X	58	43:1D.L.+1WL	-4.841	0.567	0.184	4.877	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Y	87	43:1D.L.+1WL	-2.215	26.935	0.000	26.930	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Y	57	38:1D.L.+1LL	0.274	-35.549	0.012	35.550	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Z	111	38:1D.L.+1LL	-3.478	-1.449	0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Z	2	38:1D.L.+1LL	-3.478	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rX	2	38:1D.L.+1LL	-3.478	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rX	2	38:1D.L.+1LL	-3.478	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rY	2	38:1D.L.+1LL	-3.478	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rY	2	38:1D.L.+1LL	-3.478	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rZ	2	38:1D.L.+1LL	-3.478	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rZ	2	38:1D.L.+1LL	-3.478	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Rst	57	38:1D.L.+1LL	0.274	-35.549	0.012	35.550	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum rafter deflection for PEB1 is 27.048mm and that of CSB1 is 35.549mm. The CSB1 shows a deflection greater than that of PEB1 by 31.42%.

The tables 6.9 and 6.10 give the nodal displacement summary for the rafters of PEB2 and CSB2 models. The maximum and minimum displacements in x,y and z directions

for the nodes are extracted with the tables giving the critical load combination corresponding to each node.

TABLE 6.9: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR PEB2(RAFTER)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	127	41:1D.L.+1W.L	31.652	22.365	-1.855	38.801	-0.000	-0.000	-0.003
Min X	20	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-43.618	68.527	3.921	81.325	0.000	-0.000	-0.004
Max Y	36	41:1D.L.+1W.L	5.930	75.147	-1.431	75.394	-0.000	0.000	-0.003
Min Y	20	38:1D.L.+1L.L	11.745	-59.981	0.012	61.120	0.000	0.000	0.004
Max Z	6	49:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-23.535	0.072	9.248	25.287	0.000	0.000	-0.000
Min Z	6	41:1D.L.+1W.L	27.265	-0.099	-3.272	27.461	0.000	0.000	-0.000
Max rX	3	41:1D.L.+1W.L	26.700	-0.184	-0.703	26.710	0.041	0.008	-0.001
Min rX	3	49:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-22.397	-0.039	2.117	22.497	-0.036	-0.008	0.001
Max rY	3	41:1D.L.+1W.L	26.700	-0.184	-0.703	26.710	0.041	0.008	-0.001
Min rY	4	41:1D.L.+1W.L	27.917	-0.220	-0.874	27.932	0.041	-0.008	-0.001
Max rZ	132	41:1D.L.+1W.L	10.623	51.124	-1.026	52.226	-0.000	0.000	0.011
Min rZ	134	41:1D.L.+1W.L	14.085	34.970	-1.737	37.740	-0.000	0.000	-0.010
Max Rst	52	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-42.076	73.359	3.997	84.663	0.000	-0.000	-0.004

TABLE 6.10: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR CSB2(RAFTER)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	149	47:0.9L.L.+0.9\	11.415	0.684	-0.243	11.438	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min X	131	49:0.9L.L.+0.9\	-11.678	0.552	0.307	11.695	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Y	122	47:0.9L.L.+0.9\	2.937	57.296	-0.513	57.373	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Y	127	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-0.791	-53.294	0.643	53.304	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Z	6	38:1D.L.+1L.L	0.008	-1.051	5.415	5.516	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Z	6	47:0.9L.L.+0.9\	0.498	0.914	-5.188	5.291	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rX	3	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-2.600	-0.688	-1.955	3.325	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rX	3	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-2.600	-0.688	-1.955	3.325	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rY	3	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-2.600	-0.688	-1.955	3.325	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rY	3	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-2.600	-0.688	-1.955	3.325	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rZ	3	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-2.600	-0.688	-1.955	3.325	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rZ	3	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-2.600	-0.688	-1.955	3.325	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Rst	122	47:0.9L.L.+0.9\	2.937	57.296	-0.513	57.373	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum rafter deflection for PEB2 is 75.17mm and that of CSB2 is 57.296mm. The CSB2 shows a deflection lesser than that of PEB2 by 23.77%.

The tables 6.11 and 6.12 give the nodal displacement summary for the rafters of PEB3 and CSB3 models. The maximum and minimum displacements in x,y and z directions for the nodes are extracted with the tables giving the critical load combination corresponding to each node.

TABLE 6.11: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR PEB3(RAFTER)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	216	38:1D.L.+1L.L.	8.354	-82.573	0.725	82.998	-0.000	-0.000	-0.002
Min X	232	45:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-29.338	123.015	11.883	127.022	0.001	-0.000	0.003
Max Y	232	45:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-29.338	123.015	11.883	127.022	0.001	-0.000	0.003
Min Y	219	40:1D.L.+1W.L.	-12.286	-85.122	-2.175	86.031	-0.000	-0.000	0.002
Max Z	31	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	-0.352	-0.451	84.012	84.014	0.008	0.000	0.000
Min Z	6	39:1D.L.+1W.L.	-5.855	-0.102	-10.456	11.984	0.008	-0.001	0.000
Max rX	204	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	2.115	-0.094	69.130	69.162	0.741	-0.069	0.000
Min rX	6	46:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-4.027	0.066	28.128	28.415	-0.004	0.000	0.000
Max rY	477	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	-3.048	-16.752	66.942	69.073	0.006	0.004	-0.004
Min rY	204	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	2.115	-0.094	69.130	69.162	0.741	-0.069	0.000
Max rZ	233	45:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-24.184	68.729	6.507	73.150	0.000	-0.001	0.008
Min rZ	230	45:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-20.909	44.292	19.785	52.824	0.002	-0.000	-0.007
Max Rst	224	45:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-29.338	123.015	11.891	127.022	0.001	-0.000	0.003

TABLE 6.12: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR CSB3(RAFTER)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	1065	25:1D.L.+1W.L.	37.953	1.092	0.215	37.970	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min X	1066	27:1D.L.+1W.L.	-23.373	1.034	-0.311	23.398	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Y	1704	25:1D.L.+1W.L.	7.741	512.787	1.019	512.847	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Y	1723	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	-0.771	-232.038	-1.031	232.041	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Z	2068	25:1D.L.+1W.L.	0.354	2.147	11.465	11.669	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Z	6	25:1D.L.+1W.L.	0.123	1.691	-11.193	11.320	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rX	6	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	0.034	-0.807	4.958	5.023	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rX	6	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	0.034	-0.807	4.958	5.023	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rY	6	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	0.034	-0.807	4.958	5.023	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rY	6	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	0.034	-0.807	4.958	5.023	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rZ	6	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	0.034	-0.807	4.958	5.023	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rZ	6	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	0.034	-0.807	4.958	5.023	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Rst	1704	25:1D.L.+1W.L.	7.741	512.787	1.019	512.847	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum rafter deflection for PEB3 is 123.015mm and that of CSB3 is 512.787mm. The CSB3 shows a comparatively greater deflection than that of PEB3.

The tables 6.13 and 6.14 give the nodal displacement summary for the columns of PEB1 and CSB1 models. The maximum and minimum displacements in x,y and z directions for the nodes are extracted with the tables giving the critical load combination corresponding to each node.

TABLE 6.13: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR PEB1(COLUMN)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	13	42:1D.L.+1W.L	41.599	0.166	-0.009	41.599	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min X	19	44:1D.L.+1W.L	-12.315	0.095	0.683	12.334	0.000	0.000	0.001
Max Y	13	42:1D.L.+1W.L	41.599	0.166	-0.009	41.599	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Y	53	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-0.976	-0.299	-0.680	1.226	-0.000	0.000	-0.000
Max Z	43	50:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-6.604	-0.036	1.999	6.900	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
Min Z	53	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-0.976	-0.299	-0.680	1.226	-0.000	0.000	-0.000
Max rX	3	42:1D.L.+1W.L	32.169	0.056	0.479	32.173	0.001	0.000	-0.001
Min rX	28	42:1D.L.+1W.L	32.170	0.054	-0.516	32.174	-0.001	-0.000	-0.001
Max rY	4	50:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-6.205	0.009	0.964	6.280	-0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rY	3	50:0.8L.L.+0.8\	-6.592	-0.016	0.925	6.657	-0.000	-0.000	0.000
Max rZ	14	38:1D.L.+1L.L	4.710	-0.212	-0.204	4.720	-0.000	0.000	0.003
Min rZ	14	42:1D.L.+1W.L	35.019	0.055	-0.017	35.019	0.000	-0.000	-0.004
Max Rst	18	42:1D.L.+1W.L	41.599	0.166	-0.028	41.599	-0.000	-0.000	0.000

TABLE 6.14: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR CSB1(COLUMN)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	56	38:1D.L.+1L.L	4.573	-1.052	-0.104	4.693	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min X	56	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-4.841	0.567	0.184	4.877	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Y	2	41:1D.L.+1W.L	2.388	0.920	0.728	2.661	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Y	4	38:1D.L.+1L.L	3.709	-1.598	-0.850	4.127	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Z	111	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-3.476	-1.449	0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Z	2	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-3.476	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rX	2	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-3.476	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rX	2	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-3.476	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rY	2	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-3.476	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rY	2	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-3.476	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rZ	2	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-3.476	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rZ	2	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-3.476	-1.449	-0.906	3.874	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Rst	56	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-4.841	0.567	0.184	4.877	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum column lateral deflection for PEB1 is 41.599mm and that of CSB1 is 4.573mm. The CSB1 shows a deflection lesser than that of PEB1 by 89%.

The tables 6.15 and 6.16 give the nodal displacement summary for the columns of PEB2 and CSB2 models. The maximum and minimum displacements in x,y and z directions for the nodes are extracted with the tables giving the critical load combination corresponding to each node.

TABLE 6.15: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR PEB2(COLUMN)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	16	42:1D.L.+1W.L	28.176	-0.060	-0.026	28.176	-0.000	0.000	-0.001
Min X	112	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-30.938	-0.249	1.113	30.959	-0.022	-0.005	0.001
Max Y	58	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-27.171	0.476	4.861	27.607	0.000	0.000	-0.002
Min Y	58	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-0.240	-0.709	0.003	0.749	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Z	6	49:0.8L.L.+0.8L	-23.535	0.072	9.248	25.287	0.000	0.000	-0.000
Min Z	6	41:1D.L.+1W.L	27.265	-0.099	-3.272	27.461	0.000	0.000	-0.000
Max rX	3	41:1D.L.+1W.L	26.700	-0.184	-0.703	26.710	0.041	0.008	-0.001
Min rX	113	41:1D.L.+1W.L	27.708	-0.219	0.711	27.717	-0.041	0.008	-0.001
Max rY	113	41:1D.L.+1W.L	27.708	-0.219	0.711	27.717	-0.041	0.008	-0.001
Min rY	112	41:1D.L.+1W.L	26.489	-0.178	0.853	26.504	-0.041	-0.008	-0.001
Max rZ	32	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-27.801	0.224	0.980	27.819	0.000	-0.000	0.008
Min rZ	16	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-0.058	-0.247	0.075	0.264	0.000	0.000	-0.006
Max Rst	172	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-30.913	0.042	2.994	31.058	-0.017	-0.004	-0.000

TABLE 6.16: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR CSB2(COLUMN)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	16	42:1D.L.+1W.L	28.176	-0.060	-0.026	28.176	-0.000	0.000	-0.001
Min X	112	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-30.938	-0.249	1.113	30.959	-0.022	-0.005	0.001
Max Y	58	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-27.171	0.476	4.861	27.607	0.000	0.000	-0.002
Min Y	58	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-0.240	-0.709	0.003	0.749	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Z	6	49:0.8L.L.+0.8L	-23.535	0.072	9.248	25.287	0.000	0.000	-0.000
Min Z	6	41:1D.L.+1W.L	27.265	-0.099	-3.272	27.461	0.000	0.000	-0.000
Max rX	3	41:1D.L.+1W.L	26.700	-0.184	-0.703	26.710	0.041	0.008	-0.001
Min rX	113	41:1D.L.+1W.L	27.708	-0.219	0.711	27.717	-0.041	0.008	-0.001
Max rY	113	41:1D.L.+1W.L	27.708	-0.219	0.711	27.717	-0.041	0.008	-0.001
Min rY	112	41:1D.L.+1W.L	26.489	-0.178	0.853	26.504	-0.041	-0.008	-0.001
Max rZ	32	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-27.801	0.224	0.980	27.819	0.000	-0.000	0.008
Min rZ	16	38:1D.L.+1L.L	-0.058	-0.247	0.075	0.264	0.000	0.000	-0.006
Max Rst	172	43:1D.L.+1W.L	-30.913	0.042	2.994	31.058	-0.017	-0.004	-0.000

The maximum column lateral deflection for PEB2 is 30.938mm and that of CSB2 is 11.678mm. The CSB2 shows a deflection lesser than that of PEB2 by 62.25%.

The tables 6.17 and 6.18 give the nodal displacement summary for the columns of PEB3 and CSB3 models. The maximum and minimum displacements in x,y and z directions for the nodes are extracted with the tables giving the critical load combination corresponding to each nod

TABLE 6.17: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR PEB3(COLUMN)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	3	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	6.389	-0.030	5.174	8.221	0.001	-0.002	-0.001
Min X	79	45:0.8L.L.+0.8I	-19.000	0.150	0.356	19.004	0.000	-0.001	0.005
Max Y	151	45:0.8L.L.+0.8I	-11.017	0.712	24.893	27.232	0.002	0.000	-0.002
Min Y	81	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	-2.984	-0.766	84.542	84.598	0.008	0.001	0.000
Max Z	196	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	2.096	-0.094	365.647	365.653	0.741	-0.069	0.000
Min Z	6	39:1D.L.+1W.L.	-5.855	-0.102	-10.456	11.984	0.008	-0.001	0.000
Max rX	196	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	2.096	-0.094	365.647	365.653	0.741	-0.069	0.000
Min rX	156	39:1D.L.+1W.L.	-5.815	-0.104	12.722	13.989	-0.006	-0.000	0.000
Max rY	212	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	-2.816	-0.076	53.611	53.685	0.006	0.004	0.000
Min rY	196	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	2.096	-0.094	365.647	365.653	0.741	-0.069	0.000
Max rZ	79	45:0.8L.L.+0.8I	-19.000	0.150	0.356	19.004	0.000	-0.001	0.005
Min rZ	74	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	6.133	-0.148	4.370	7.532	0.001	-0.002	-0.002
Max Rst	196	47:1D.L.+1E.Q	2.096	-0.094	365.647	365.653	0.741	-0.069	0.000

TABLE 6.18: NODAL DISPLACEMENT SUMMARY FOR CSB3(COLUMN)

	Node	L/C	X (mm)	Y (mm)	Z (mm)	Resultant (mm)	rX (rad)	rY (rad)	rZ (rad)
Max X	1065	25:1D.L.+1W.L	37.953	1.092	0.215	37.970	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min X	1066	27:1D.L.+1W.L	-23.373	1.034	-0.311	23.398	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Y	1745	25:1D.L.+1W.L	26.653	2.558	-5.088	27.255	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Y	113	25:1D.L.+1W.L	3.108	-2.017	6.532	7.509	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Z	181	25:1D.L.+1W.L	9.420	1.578	7.803	12.333	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Z	1949	25:1D.L.+1W.L	9.356	1.579	-6.590	11.552	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rX	23	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	-1.499	-0.674	-2.105	2.671	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rX	23	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	-1.499	-0.674	-2.105	2.671	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rY	23	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	-1.499	-0.674	-2.105	2.671	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rY	23	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	-1.499	-0.674	-2.105	2.671	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max rZ	23	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	-1.499	-0.674	-2.105	2.671	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min rZ	23	24:1D.L.+1L.L.	-1.499	-0.674	-2.105	2.671	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Rst	1065	25:1D.L.+1W.L	37.953	1.092	0.215	37.970	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum column lateral deflection for PEB3 is 30.938mm and that of CSB3 is 37.953mm. The CSB3 shows a deflection greater than that of PEB3 by 22.67%.

Fig 6.1 & 6.2 show a comparative study on rafter and column deflections for models on the basis of the results obtained which are described in previous paragraphs.

FIG 6.1 - COMPARITIVE STUDY OF RAFTER DEFLECTIONS BETWEEN PEB AND CSB BUILDING MODELS

FIG 6.2 - COMPARITIVE STUDY OF COLUMN DEFLECTIONS BETWEEN PEN AND CSB BUILDINGS

The truss buildings show reduced joint displacements as compared to PEB buildings except the last case where CSB shows greater displacements as compared to PEB. It is

also observed previously that on comparing reaction forces,CSB showed lesser reaction forces as compared to PEB.

6.2.3 Comparison of Member Forces

The tables 6.19 and 6.20 give beam force summary for PEB1 and CSB1. The maximum axial, shear, moment and torsion values against the load combinations are given.

TABLE 6.19: BEAM FORCE SUMMARY FOR PEB1

	Beam	L/C	d (m)	Axial			Shear			Torsion	Bending	
				Fx (kN)	Fy (kN)	Fz (kN)	Mx (kNm)	My (kNm)	Mz (kNm)			
Max Fx	36	56:GENERATE	0.000	209.284	1.215	-0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000		
Min Fx	38	64:GENERATE	0.000	-112.151	1.519	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000		
Max Fy	10	56:GENERATE	0.000	85.655	156.949	0.025	-0.004	0.001	420.106			
Min Fy	67	58:GENERATE	3.824	110.113	-126.905	-0.093	0.002	0.000	338.176			
Max Fz	41	71:GENERATE	0.000	40.608	3.283	16.115	0.000	-10.925	11.492			
Min Fz	3	71:GENERATE	3.500	20.358	3.283	-16.117	-0.000	-10.925	11.492			
Max Mx	22	56:GENERATE	0.000	-22.029	21.418	-0.051	0.017	-0.003	74.656			
Min Mx	2	56:GENERATE	0.000	-22.026	21.422	0.051	-0.017	0.003	74.667			
Max My	3	67:GENERATE	3.500	11.498	-3.239	16.059	-0.000	10.730	-11.335			
Min My	3	71:GENERATE	3.500	20.358	3.283	-16.117	-0.000	-10.925	11.492			
Max Mz	10	56:GENERATE	0.000	85.655	156.949	0.025	-0.004	0.001	420.106			
Min Mz	10	64:GENERATE	0.000	-46.002	-84.804	-0.032	0.002	-0.000	-258.876			

TABLE 6.20: BEAM FORCE SUMMARY FOR CSB1

	Beam	L/C	d (m)	Axial			Shear			Torsion	Bending	
				Fx (kN)	Fy (kN)	Fz (kN)	Mx (kNm)	My (kNm)	Mz (kNm)			
Max Fx	96	16:GENERATE	3.059	648.329	-31.583	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000			
Min Fx	90	14:GENERATE	0.000	-617.082	0.243	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Max Fy	96	14:GENERATE	0.000	627.410	31.620	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Min Fy	96	14:GENERATE	3.059	632.157	-31.620	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000			
Max Fz	305	25:GENERATE	7.000	17.015	-0.000	51.975	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000			
Min Fz	305	25:GENERATE	0.000	0.939	0.000	-51.975	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Max Mx	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	253.959	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Min Mx	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	253.959	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Max My	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	253.959	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Min My	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	253.959	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Max Mz	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	253.959	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Min Mz	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	253.959	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000			

The maximum Axial Force in PEB1 is 209.284 Kn and in CSB1 is 648.329 Kn. Hence it is seen that the axial force in CSB1 is greater than in PEB1 by a factor of 3 as the frame action in Pre-Engineered Building system offers resistance against moment which reduces the axial force considerably.

The tables 6.21 and 6.22 give beam force summary for PEB2 and CSB2. The maximum axial, shear, moment and torsion values against the load combinations are given.

TABLE 6.21: BEAM FORCE SUMMARY FOR PEB2

	Beam	L/C	d (m)	Axial	Shear		Torsion	Bending	
				Fx (kN)	Fy (kN)	Fz (kN)	Mx (kNm)	My (kNm)	Mz (kNm)
Max Fx	56	16:GENERATE	11.000	485.307	20.893	-0.035	-0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Fx	205	24:GENERATE	4.589	-231.529	126.630	0.339	-0.001	0.740	-555.628
Max Fy	97	14:GENERATE	0.000	3.324	220.648	0.056	-0.001	-0.047	1.12E+3
Min Fy	181	16:GENERATE	5.099	170.496	-261.875	-0.327	0.001	-0.977	1.26E+3
Max Fz	8	25:GENERATE	11.000	0.904	-0.000	81.675	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
Min Fz	8	25:GENERATE	0.000	-36.839	-0.000	-81.675	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Mx	16	25:GENERATE	0.000	98.786	4.382	-0.001	0.040	-0.069	3.349
Min Mx	4	25:GENERATE	0.000	69.683	6.751	-0.017	-0.039	0.008	27.016
Max My	8	29:GENERATE	5.500	97.350	0.000	-0.000	0.000	224.606	-0.000
Min My	8	25:GENERATE	5.500	-7.758	-0.000	-0.000	0.000	-224.606	0.000
Max Mz	181	16:GENERATE	5.099	170.496	-261.875	-0.327	0.001	-0.977	1.26E+3
Min Mz	189	24:GENERATE	5.099	-118.832	141.277	0.301	-0.001	0.875	-672.664

TABLE 6.22: BEAM FORCE SUMMARY FOR CSB2

	Beam	L/C	d (m)	Axial	Shear		Torsion	Bending	
				Fx (kN)	Fy (kN)	Fz (kN)	Mx (kNm)	My (kNm)	Mz (kNm)
Max Fx	129	26:GENERATE	0.000	1.63E+3	40.568	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Fx	186	26:GENERATE	0.000	-1.74E+3	3.488	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Fy	188	26:GENERATE	0.000	1.12E+3	83.796	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Fy	188	26:GENERATE	8.158	1.11E+3	-83.796	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
Max Fz	640	25:GENERATE	7.000	236.765	-0.000	51.975	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
Min Fz	640	25:GENERATE	0.000	217.601	0.000	-51.975	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Mx	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	231.324	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Mx	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	231.324	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max My	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	231.324	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min My	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	231.324	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Mz	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	231.324	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Mz	1	9:GENERATE	0.000	231.324	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum Axial Force in PEB2 is 485.307 Kn and in CSB2 is 1.63×10^3 Kn. Hence it is seen that the axial force in CSB2 is greater than in PEB2 by a factor of 3 as the frame action in Pre-Engineered Building system offers resistance against moment which reduces the axial force considerably.

The tables 6.23 and 6.24 give beam force summary for PEB3 and CSB3. The maximum axial, shear, moment and torsion values against the load combinations are given.

TABLE 6.23: BEAM FORCE SUMMARY FOR PEB3

	Beam	L/C	d (m)	Axial	Shear		Torsion	Bending	
				Fx (kN)	Fy (kN)	Fz (kN)	Mx (kNm)	My (kNm)	Mz (kNm)
Max Fx	265	30:GENERATE	0.000	1.16E+3	-144.676	-4.595	-0.158	-0.374	390.797
Min Fx	5	32:GENERATE	0.000	-1.04E+3	23.354	-17.676	-61.674	94.446	38.778
Max Fy	8	26:GENERATE	0.000	409.669	507.730	0.229	0.002	-0.000	3.36E+3
Min Fy	272	28:GENERATE	9.045	801.655	-607.046	2.112	0.040	17.026	5.5E+3
Max Fz	765	25:GENERATE	11.500	-28.896	-2.475	91.165	-0.000	66.443	28.465
Min Fz	173	30:GENERATE	0.000	14.714	-24.823	-245.633	0.000	98.253	-9.929
Max Mx	146	30:GENERATE	0.000	313.718	24.654	-0.702	19.729	8.319	37.381
Min Mx	5	30:GENERATE	0.000	764.272	23.810	-16.067	-78.036	24.151	33.239
Max My	765	29:GENERATE	5.750	161.963	2.222	4.132	0.000	269.248	-12.776
Min My	711	22:GENERATE	5.750	73.801	-2.892	0.383	0.000	-222.455	16.629
Max Mz	272	28:GENERATE	9.045	801.655	-607.046	2.112	0.040	17.026	5.5E+3
Min Mz	274	28:GENERATE	2.713	734.050	-9.604	0.430	0.040	1.337	-2.03E+3

TABLE 6.24: BEAM FORCE SUMMARY FOR CSB3

	Beam	L/C	d (m)	Axial	Shear		Torsion	Bending	
				Fx (kN)	Fy (kN)	Fz (kN)	Mx (kNm)	My (kNm)	Mz (kNm)
Max Fx	771	9:GENERATEC	4.012	1.51E+3	-10.086	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
Min Fx	2696	9:GENERATEC	0.000	-1.45E+3	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Fy	214	9:GENERATEC	0.000	206.296	13.868	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Fy	214	9:GENERATEC	5.517	204.138	-13.868	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000	-0.000
Max Fz	1	9:GENERATEC	0.000	179.062	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Fz	1	9:GENERATEC	0.000	179.062	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Mx	1	9:GENERATEC	0.000	179.062	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Mx	1	9:GENERATEC	0.000	179.062	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max My	1	9:GENERATEC	0.000	179.062	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min My	1	9:GENERATEC	0.000	179.062	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Max Mz	1	9:GENERATEC	0.000	179.062	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Min Mz	1	9:GENERATEC	0.000	179.062	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

The maximum Axial Force in PEB3 is 1.16×10^3 Kn and in CSB3 is 1.51×10^3 Kn. Hence it is seen that the axial force in CSB3 is greater than in PEB3 by a factor of 1.3. There is no considerable reduction in axial force due to the frame action in large span buildings.

Fig 6.3, Fig 6.4 and Fig 6.5 give the comparative study of maximum member forces between CSB and PEB Models.

FIG 6.3 - COMPARITIVE STUDY OF FX BETWEEN CSB AND PEB BUILDINGS

FIG 6.4 - COMPARITIVE STUDY OF FY BETWEEN CSB AND PEB BUILDINGS

FIG 6.5 - COMPARITIVE STUDY OF FZ BETWEEN CSB AND PEB BUILDINGS

6.2.4 Comparison of Steel Takeoff

Refer the table extracted from STAAP.Pro to find the steel takeoff of steel building models:

TABLE 6.25: STEEL TAKEOFF FOR THE MODELS

For PEB1		
PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
MembNo:1	47.17	73.89
Tapered MembNo:2	36.95	42.992
Tapered MembNo:5	28	18.601
SA ISA90X90X8	276.71	58.668
SA ISA100X100X10	158.28	46.446
Tapered MembNo:42	36.95	37.884
ST UC203X203X52	31	15.784
		TOTAL = 267.545
For CSB1		
PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
LD L60405	100.94	30.316
LD L50355	217	55.064
LD L25204	21.12	2.24

PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
LD L20203	126.26	9.036
LD L40355	12.24	2.729
LD L30254	57.46	7.519
LD L25205	18.62	2.436
LD L25203	3	0.243
LD L30304	10.56	1.507
LD L35304	54.8	8.582
LD L40304	10.06	1.685
LD L35255	3.06	0.543
LD L25254	9	1.062
LD L30203	9	0.818
LD L35254	4.5	0.647
LD L60406	25.71	9.199
LD L40305	3.06	0.634
LD L35305	3.06	0.591
LD L30256	3.06	0.585
LD L25206	3	0.461
LD L40406	6.12	1.735
LD L40356	7	1.86
LD L50507	139.14	58.201
LD L60608	93.72	53.6
		TOTAL= 251.292 KN
For PEB2		
PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
ST UB305X165X40	109.58	43.201
Tapered MembNo:8	154	165.718
ST UC254X254X89.5	108	94.581
Tapered MembNo:17	229.19	193.245
Tapered MembNo:19	61.19	48.565
Tapered MembNo:20	122.38	134.978
Tapered MembNo:22	244.75	188.62
SA ISA90X90X6	709.87	114.518
SA ISA120X120X10	480.71	172.085
		TOTAL = 1155.511 KN
For CSB2		
PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
LD L60608	471.95	269.924

PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
LD L50355	515.55	130.821
LD L40355	79.49	17.728
LD L40305	37.44	7.756
LD L30254	235.94	30.871
LD L25203	60.23	4.884
LD L40356	7.55	2.005
LD L35305	50.41	9.743
LD L35304	168.82	26.439
LD L40304	53.49	8.96
LD L50507	64	26.771
LD L50508	12	5.698
LD L80608	481.91	324.82
LD L60407	108	44.748
LD L60409	32.16	16.926
LD L20203	61.47	4.399
LD L25204	37.49	3.976
LD L50356	8	2.419
LD L40405	8	1.903
LD L808010	151.1	145.126
LD L60609	125.51	80.24
LD L80609	217.03	163.712
LD L806010	222.88	185.799
LD L60406	68	24.332
LD L40406	8	2.268
LD L60405	172	51.658
LD L60408	56	26.366
LD L808012	73.14	83.375
LD L10010014	12	19.983
		TOTAL = 1723.650
PEB3		
PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
Tapered MembNo:1	958.6	2465.449
ST UC356X406X235	180.9	415.505
Tapered MembNo:9	262.3	729.023
STUC356X406X287	171	480.783
Tapered MembNo:173	333.9	759.241
Tapered MembNo:174	262.3	748.568
Tapered MembNo:175	1573.81	4128.713
SA ISA80X80X6	2159.99	308.298

PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
SA ISA150X150X16	761.96	534.998
		TOTAL = 10570.578
CSB3		
PROFILE	LENGTH(METER)	WEIGHT(KN)
LD ISA130X130X12	496	227.853
SD ISA130X130X8	5239.06	1633.993
LD ISA200X200X25	2798.41	4045.806
LD ISA150X150X16	4110.15	2885.843
SD ISA90X90X6	3445.33	555.804
LD ISA120X120X8	689.94	199.283
SD ISA100X100X6	69.46	12.485
LD ISA180X180X15	480.75	384.821
LD ISA130X130X16	760.75	458.173
LD ISA150X150X20	891.84	770.064
SD ISA200X200X12	296.89	213.93
LD ISA180X180X18	115.43	109.78
		TOTAL = 11497.833

The steel takeoff for PEB1 and CSB1 are 267.545Kn and 251.292Kn respectively. The steel takeoff for CSB1 is lesser than PEB1 6.075% by as compared to PEB1.

The steel takeoff for PEB2 and CSB2 are 1155.511Kn and 1723.650Kn respectively. The steel takeoff for CSB2 is greater than PEB2 by 49.16% as compared to PEB2.

The steel takeoff for PEB3 and CSB3 are 10570.578Kn and 11497.833Kn respectively. The steel takeoff for CSB3 is greater than PEB3 by 8.77% as compared to PEB3.

Fig 6.6 gives the comparative study of steel takeoff between CSB and PEB models.

FIG 6.6 - COMPARITIVE STUDY OF STEEL TAKE-OFF BETWEEN CSB AND PEB BUILDINGS

It is observed that there is economy in steel in case of medium span buildings as compared to small span and large span buildings. Fig 6.6 gives the comparative study of steel take-off between CSB and PEB models.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

5.1 General

There is a rapid growth in demand for Pre Engineered Buildings owing to the gain in economy due to quicker construction, better quality control and saving on steel quantity. The building system can have variety of architectural looks due to wide variety of metal wall panels, fascia, canopy types that are available. Hence there is a scope for large number of studies to be done on this topic so as to check the extend of economy that could be arrived at.

The major objective of the present study is to do a comparative study between Pre-Engineered Building and truss steel building for varying spans and hence arrive at findings related to the most economic building structure configuration for a given span. In the following results PEB refers to the Pre-Engineered Building and CSB refers to Conventional Steel Building which is taken as truss building configuration in the given study.

5.2 Conclusions

Based on the study undertaken the following conclusions were obtained:

1) PEB is found to be more economical than CSB for mid and large span industrial building structures in the range of 40-90m. There is an increase in steel consumption in CSB as compared to PEB for the 15m building in terms of total steel in superstructure. The reactions in CSB1 is greater than that in PEB1. Since the variation

in the reaction forces comes approximately in the range of 30 - 50%, one can deduce that the overall economy in steel consumption for CSB1 over PEB1 will lesser. This increase in steel consumption in PEB1 over CSB1 is due to more economical truss member sections which are lighter in comparison to the pre-engineered member sections. The heavier built-up sections also increase self weight and subsequent member forces.

2)The size of steel cross sections was greatly influenced by the serviceability requirements in CSB models.The CSB model for 90m(large span building) showed great joint displacements when designed for strength and sections had to be revised for bringing displacements under permissible limits.The PEB model required additional bracings and larger brace,tie cross sections along with greater depths for deflection control.This greatly influenced the extend of economic variation on using pre-engineered building system.

3)Due to the rigidity of the joints,PEB model members carried lesser forces than CSB and also due to the variation of member profiles along the length,there was more economy in material in PEB than in CSB.The reduction in weight due to optimized section profiles helped in bringing down the overall member forces and the dual system of rigid frame in lateral direction and truss action in form of ties in longitudinal direction in pre-engineered buildings helped in enhanced performance.

4)The key comparative analysis results are as follows:

1)PEB1&CSB1(15x30m)

- The lateral support reaction forces F_x & F_z reduced by 52.22% and 27.22% in PEB1 as compared to CSB1.

-The vertical support reaction reduced by 59.44% in PEB1 as compared to CSB1.

-The CSB1 showed rafter deflection greater than that of PEB1 by 31.42%.

-The CSB1 showed maximum column lateral deflection lesser than PEB1 by 89%

-The steel take off in CSB1 is lesser than PEB1 by 6.075%.

2)PEB2&CSB2(40x80m)

- The lateral support reaction forces F_x & F_z reduced by 81.64% and 76.95% in PEB2 as compared to CSB2.

-The vertical support reaction reduced by 57.42% in PEB2 as compared to CSB2.

-The CSB2 showed rafter deflection lesser than that of PEB2 by 23.77%.

-The CSB2 showed maximum column lateral deflection lesser than PEB2 by 62.25%

-The steel take off in CSB2 is greater than PEB2 by 49.16%.

3)PEB3&CSB3(90x180m)

- The lateral support reaction forces F_x & F_z reduced by 18.52% and 28.14% in PEB3 as compared to CSB3.
- The vertical support reaction is greater by 20.63% in PEB3 as compared to CSB3.
- The CSB3 showed maximum column lateral deflection lesser than PEB3 by 22.67%
- The steel take off in CSB3 is greater than PEB3 by 8.77%.

5.3Future scope of work

The present work can be extended further by incorporating some of the aspects that were not taken into consideration:

- 1) The PEB models were considered with a constant spacing and the optimization of model did not include variation of spacing. Hence additional parameters of height, roof slope and bay spacing can be varied so as to optimize the model further and arrive at an economic model.
- 2) The effect of number and position of longitudinal bracings on models can be studied to optimize the model further
- 3) Software using iteration procedure can be developed to aid in optimization of model.
- 4) The various building configurations using Pre-Engineered Building concepts can be compared and assessed
- 5) Study on mixed building systems using hot rolled sections, built up sections and cold formed sections from economy considerations.

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Publications

With respect to the work on the thesis “Comparitive Study of Pre-Engineered Building and Truss Arrangement Building for varying spans “, the following papers have been published.

- “Comparitive Study of Pre-Engineered Building and Truss Arrangement Building for varying spans” in IJERT, Volume 10, Issue 10, October - 2021
- “Study on Structural Design Optimization of Steel Building” in IJEAST, 2022, Volume 6, Issue 10, ISSN No. 2455-2143, Pages 202-207